

Comparative Evaluation of Different Packaging Materials for Sorghum Seed Quality over Various Storage Periods

*Fekede Tena

Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research (EIAR), Assosa, Ethiopia

*Corresponding author: [Fekede Tena](#)

Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research (EIAR), Assosa, Ethiopia

Abstract

The experiment was conducted on the Assosa-1 variety of sorghum for physical and physiological studies with respect to storage period and packaging materials in the 2019 and 2020 cropping seasons. The experiment was laid out as a completely randomized design in a factorial arrangement replicated four times. 30 kilograms of pre-basic seed were stored for 24 months using airtight packing materials such as polypropylene bags with polyethylene sheet lining, PICS bags, Super Grain Pro bags, metal silos, non-airtight polypropylene bags, and zero fly bags. The treatment comprises one variety and six packaging materials and five (0, 6, 12, 18, and 24 months) storage periods. The outcome of laboratory analysis indicated packaging materials and storage periods significantly ($p \leq 0.001$) interacted to affect all the seed quality parameters studied. Increased moisture content was directly related to atmospheric relative humidity and insect pest infestations for non-airtight packing materials. In addition, as the storage period increased, the mean values of speed of germination, standard germination, seedling dry weight, and vigor index significantly decreased. Airtight packaging materials showed minimum variation in the mean values of the seed quality parameter up to 18 months of seed storage. Among the airtight packaging materials, specifically PICS bags are superior in preserving seed quality.

Keywords: Bags, packaging materials, quality seed, storage period, sorghum.

1. Introduction

Sorghum occupies fifth rank in the world among the cereals crops based on their sequence of importance wheat, rice, maize and barley. Sorghum is a crop preferred for regions and agro ecological zones with unreliable rainfall (Pursoglove, 1975). Because of attribution of the crops to its drought resistance, as well as used as staple food. It is the major source of energy and protein for millions of people living in semi-arid tropics (Kidane, 1982).

Sorghum usually cultivated in range of altitudes 0 to 2500 meters above sea level. In Ethiopia the crop is dominant in the low land area where droughts and poor harvest common occurrences. Agro-ecology of sorghum under which seed produced contributed to seed deterioration after physiological maturity and storage to next growing season for high humid low land area like Benishangul Gumuz region. Whatsoever is sorghum remains critically important for rural food security in the region.

Seed quality has major direct influence on crop production and productivity. Storage structures such as local gotera, clay pots, and muddy panted structure made bamboo, polyethylene bags and newly introduced hermetic bags has been used in the region for storage. Newly introduced storage materials have been provided by government and NGOs varies in keeping quality of seed for certain period of times. But farmers and sorghum seed produces complain for some of the seed storage materials available on the market. Proper packaging and ideal conditions of storage are required to maintain seed quality. Rao et al. (2006) reported that packaging container, storage condition and duration affects seed quality (viability and vigour). Seeds deterioration starts after physiological maturity in the field before and after harvesting through processing to storage until seeds become acceptable for planting (El-Borai et al., 1993). The quantity of seeds, type of package, duration of storage and prevailing environmental conditions determines how we pack the seeds.

Proper seed and grain storage materials have not been addressed to keep sorghum seed quality for certain period of time to introduce for sorghum seed producers and farmers. So based on this activity was conducted to determine effectiveness of different packaging materials for sorghum seed quality over various storage periods.

2. Materials and Methods

The research conducted in Benshangul Gumuz region of the Ethiopian in 2019 and 2020 cropping season. Assosa -1 variety of sorghum, six packaging materials (PICS bag, Polypropylene bag, Metal silo, Polypropylene bags with polyethylene sheet lining, Zero fly and Super grain bags) and five (0, 6, 12, 18 and 24) storage month were used as treatment combination for laboratory analysis. Experiment was arranged as factorial in CRD replicated four times. 30kgs of pre-basic seeds were stored and representative samples from each packing materials drawn after every month of storage and tested in the laboratory for two years. During investigation seed quality data parameters such as moisture, thousand seed weight, standard germination, dry weight of seedlings, vigor index were recorded. The data collection was carried out as prescribed by (ISTA, 1999.). All data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the Generalized Linear Model (GLM) method of SAS (SAS, 2002). Differences between treatment means were separated using the Turkey's Student zed Range (HSD) test at 5% level of significance.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1 Meteorological Data during Seed Storage

Maximum temperature (33 °c) was recorded in the month of April 2020. Maximum RH (74%) was recorded in the month of May 2021 while the lowest RH (19%) observed in the month of April of 2019.

Table 1 Meteorological data during seed storage of 2019/2020

Storage period(month)	Month	RH	Minimum Temperature (°c)	Maximum Temperature (°c)
0	Apr-19	19	16.8	32.8
6	Oct-20	73	16	25.4
12	Apr-20	25	14.2	33
18	Oct-21	73	14.7	25.8
24	May-21	74	16.7	25.2

3.2 Moisture Content

The analysis of variance showed that interaction effect of storage period and packaging materials significantly ($P < 0.001$) influenced percentage of moisture content of the seeds (Table 2). The seed was stored at the beginning with MC% of 8.6. The highest MC (15.57%) was recorded when the seed stored for 18 months in the packaging material of Zero fly bags. But the lowest 7.8% MC was observed after 12 months storage of seed in PICS bags. An increase of MC% in Polypropylene bag and Zero fly was due to high infestation of seeds with seed born insect pest and absorption of high humidity from atmosphere. The population of the pest reduced after storage for 18 months and the stored seeds entirely changed to fine particles. Then large numbers of insect pests (weevils) died and the living insect population decreased. The moisture content continuously increased at storage periods of 18 and 24 due to high atmospheric humidity. These finding in line with Bakhtavar et al. (2019) Hermetic Super bag maintained seed moisture up to 70% RH. At higher level of RH, moisture contents increased to some extent (1–2%) in Super bag, whereas this increase was much higher in conventional packaging materials (>9% higher than original SMC at 90% RH). The increase in insect population in the grain might due to higher moisture content and aeration which enhanced grain deterioration (Monira et al., 2012). JBP, PPL, HDPEV, MCPV, ALPEV and PICS treatments were observed free from insect infestation throughout the storage period.

Table 2 The interaction effect of storage period and packaging materials on moisture content, in Asossa during the main cropping season of 2019/2020

Percentage mean values of moisture content					
PM	Storage month				
	0	6	12	18	24
G	8.6k	8.6k	8.3k	9.77gh	10.7fg
MS	8.6k	8.7i-k	8.3k	9.67hi	9.6h-j
PC	8.6k	8.5k	7.8k	9.63hij	11f
PE	8.6k	8.65jk	8.4k	8.57k	11.3f
PP	8.6k	13.75cd	12.83de	13.93c	14.05bc
ZF	8.6k	13.45c-e	12.58e	15.57a	14.92ab
CV	3.47				
HSD(0.05)	0.98				
F .value	<0.0001				

Means followed by the same letter within a column are not significantly different at 5% level of significance. HSD = Tukey's student zed range test; CV = Coefficient of variation; G = Super grain pro; MS = Metal silo; PP = Polypropylene; PE = Polypropylene bags with Polyethylene sheet lining; ZF = Zero fly; PC=PICS bag

3.1 Analytical Purity

In this study, purity was done only on pure seeds and inert matter basis because initially pure seeds free of weeds and other crop seed were stored.

Table 3 The interaction effect of storage period and packaging materials on pure seed, in Asossa during the main cropping season of 2019/2020

Percentage mean values of Pure seed					
PM	Storage month				
	0	6	12	18	24
G	99.75a	99.65a	99.64a	99.55a	95.25c
MS	99.75a	99.65a	99.59a	99.55a	95c
PC	99.75a	99.56a	99.55a	99.55a	95.28c
PE	99.75a	99.71a	98.73ab	98.1ab	95.56c
PP	99.75a	94.84c	88.11d	41.53e	0g
ZF	99.75a	96.6cb	95c	88.12d	8.89f
CV	1.00				
HSD(0.05)	2.47				
F .value	<0.0001				

Means followed by the same letter within a column are not significantly different at 5% level of significance. HSD = Tukey's student zed range test; CV = Coefficient of variation; G = Super grain pro; MS = Metal silo; PP = Polypropylene; PE = Polypropylene bags with Polyethylene sheet lining; ZF = Zero fly; PC = PICS bag.

The mean value of interaction effect of storage period and packaging materials for percentage of pure seed ($p < 0.001$) showed significant different (Table 3). The highest (99.71) mean percentage values of pure seeds observed after storage of six months from the seed sample taken from Polypropylene bags with polyethylene sheet lining bags. While the lowest (0%) was recorded for seed sampled from Polypropylene bags at stored period of 24 months. An increase of inert matter was due to multiplication and infestation of weevils in Polypropylene bags and Zero Fly bags. The optimum temperature of 25°C and relative humidity of 73% at storage periods of sixth months was favourable for the development of storage insect species. However, increases in mortality of insects were observed after storage of 12 months because of reduced relativity humidity and high temperature. The outcome in comparable with N.d.G.White et al. (1995) who reported that mortality of immature and adult insects rapidly increased when exposed to carbon dioxide levels of 7–19% and defined the level that would kill 95% *Tribolium castaneum* adult population as 20% in five days. Zero Fly bags are chemical incorporated bag among the other packaging materials. According to the experiments it can preserve sorghum seed purity for 12 months better than Polypropylene bags. All air tight storage materials such as Super grain pro bags; Metal silo, PICS bags and Polypropylene bags with polyethylene sheet lining can be used for grain storage for more than two years to protect the seed from weevils.

3.2.1 Thousand Seed Weight (TSW)

The interaction effect of storage time and packaging materials significantly ($P < 0.01$) affected TSW (Table 4). The highest (28.12g) mean value of TSW was observed for Zero Fly bags after storage of 18 months and followed by (27.37g) Polypropylene bags after storage of 6 months. TSW of seed sampled from Super grain pro bags, Metal silo, PICS bags & Polypropylene bags with polyethylene sheet lining packaging materials showed statistically non-significant difference after storage of six 12 and 18 months. Even though after 18 and 24 months of storage the TSW showed slightly increase than 6 and 12 months of storage moreover insect infestation did not observed. This might be due to protection of insect infestation and limited air circulation which hinders insect reproduction. The lowest TSW was recorded for seed stored for 24 months with packaging materials of Zero Fly bags followed by Polypropylene bags. Variations in the mean value of TSW among storage times and packaging materials might have been due to high infestation of weevils and respiration of insects' increases the moisture of the seeds resulted in TSW increase. An increase of TSW after storage of 6 months was due rises of RH of atmospheric temperature. Khadtar, U. M., A. K. Shinde, P. P. Patil, and S. G. Bhave(2018) reported that storing the cowpea seeds in aluminium foil bag is storage materials due to highest germination percentage, vigour index and speed of germination and lower seed moisture content, insect infestation and electrical conductivity up to the month of storage 11th.

Table 4 The interaction effect of storage period and packaging materials on thousand seeds weight, in Asossa during the main cropping season of 2019/2020

Percentage mean values of TSW					
PM	Storage month				
	0	6	12	18	24
G	21.3e-g	22.21c-g	21.91c-g	23.38c-f	24.31bc
MS	21.3e-g	21.4d-g	21e-g	22.37c-g	22.3c-g
PC	21.3 e-g	21.5d-g	20.8fg	22.63c-g	24b-d
PE	21.3 e-g	21.97c-g	20.72g	20.89fg	23.62b-e
PP	21.3 e-g	27.37a	21.62d-g	16.12h	13.62hi
ZF	21.3 e-g	26.00ab	20.65g	28.12a	12.55i
CV	4.43				
HSD(0.05)	2.64				
F .value	<0.0002				

Means followed by the same letter within a column are not significantly different at 5% level of significance. HSD = Tukey's student zed range test; CV = Coefficient of variation; G = Super grain pro; MS = Metal silo; PP = Polypropylene; PE = Polypropylene bags with Polyethylene sheet lining; ZF = Zero fly; PC=PICS bag

3.2.1 Speed of Germination

Significant differences of mean speed of germination were observed for seeds under different storage time and packaging materials ($P < 0.001$). Daily germinated seedling counts were used to calculate speed of germination after 4 days of seed sowing. The highest 21.78 mean values of speed of germination were recorded for seed tested after storage of 12 months for packaging materials PICS bags while the lowest recorded for seed sampled from Polypropylene bags after 24 months of storage. Seed sample of sorghum tested from air tight packaging materials recorded higher mean than non-air tight bags after 12 months of storage period (Table 5). In addition, air tight packaging materials revealed superior average values of speed of germination at all periods of storage. The observation showed that speed of germination somewhat uniform for all air tight packaging materials at the end of all storage periods ranging from 17.44 to 21.78 and decreased for non-air tight packaging materials as storage period increases. The mean values of speed of germination recorded during storage of 6th and 18 months lower than that of 12 and 24 months. This was due to unfavorable cold environmental temperature which is not suitable for sorghum seed germination occurred in months August. The speed of germination of sorghum stored for different period times revealed that an increase of storage period result in reduction in speed of germination. Similar trend was recorded by Basave Gowda and Nanja reddy Y. A. (2008) reported that speed of germination decreased with storage duration mainly due to decreased germination percentage.

Table 5 The interaction effect of storage period and packaging materials on speed of germination, in Asossa during the main cropping season of 2019/2020

Percentage mean values of speed of germination					
PM	Storage month				
	0	6	12	18	24
G	19.15b-e	17.72e	21.41a	19.09b-e	19.82a-d
MS	19.15 b-e	17.82ed	21.77a	19.26 b-e	20.69ab
PC	19.15 b-e	17.44e	21.78a	19.07 b-e	20.23a-c
PE	19.15 b-e	17.66e	21.77a	18.34c-e	20.12a-c
PP	19.15 b-e	9.98g	15.37f	0.44i	0.23i
ZF	19.15 b-e	9.44g	10.16g	2.99h	2.55h
CV	4.6				
HSD(0.05)	2.02				
F .value	<.0001				

Means followed by the same letter within a column are not significantly different at 5% level of significance. HSD = Tukey's student zed range test; CV = Coefficient of variation; G = Super grain pro; MS = Metal silo; PP = Polypropylene; PE = Polypropylene bags with Polyethylene sheet lining; ZF = Zero fly; PC = PICS bag.

3.3 Physiological Quality Analysis

3.3.1 Germination Test

Treatments differed significantly in the germination percent due to storage period as well as storage materials (Table 6). Interaction effect of storage period and packaging materials significantly differences ($P < 0.001$). The highest (97.75%) mean value of standard germination was recorded for storage period of 12 months of packaging materials of PICS bags and the lowest values also recorded for Polypropylene bags and Zero fly bags after two years of storage period (Table 6). Statistically non-significant difference was observed for packaging materials such as Super grain bags, Metal silo, PICS bags and Polypropylene bags stored at all storage months. It is clear from the results that the storability of sorghum seeds is superior under oxygen limiting storage bags at room temperature throughout the storage period. Similar results are also observed as decrease in germination during storage was also reported Jagtap (2006) in sorghum. Owolade et al. (2011) suggested that air tight aluminium can containers as best sorghum storage option for farmer under ambient condition (28-32°C) with no modern storage facilities.

Table 6 The interaction effect of storage period and packaging materials on standard germination in Asossa during the main cropping season of 2019/2020

Percentage mean values of standard germination					
PM	Storage month				
	0	6	12	18	24
G	80b	97.5a	96.5a	95.5a	90.5a
MS	80b	96.75a	97a	95a	88.25ab
PC	80b	95.25a	97.75a	95.5a	91.25a
PE	80b	97a	96a	93a	93a
PP	80b	59c	63.5c	2.25f	0f
ZF	80b	60.5c	38.75d	14.25e	0f
CV	4.88				
HSD(0.05)	9.9552				
F .value	<0.0001				

Means followed by the same letter within a column are not significantly different at 5% level of significance. HSD = Tukey's student zed range test; CV = Coefficient of variation; G = Super grain pro; MS = Metal silo; PP = Polypropylene; PE = Polypropylene bags with Polyethylene sheet lining; ZF = Zero fly; PC=PICS bag

3.3.2 Seedling Dry Weight

The influence of different packing materials and storage condition on seedling dry weight (mg) indicated significant differences between treatments during storage period (Table 7). The main effect of packaging materials and duration of seed storage significantly affected seedling dry weight of the seeds ($P < 0.001$). Seedling dry weight of sorghum before stored in different packaging materials greater than those after storage of different periods. The outcome of the experiment revealed that an increase of storage period result in decreased seedling dry weight. Zero seedling dry weight was due to totally damages of seeds by insect pest for 18 and 24 months storage periods. The higher (0.26) mean weight values of the seedling was recorded for seed stored in Super grain bags at 6 months of storage. In addition, better seedling dry weight also recorded at the same storage period for all packaging materials.

Table 7 The interaction effect of storage period and packaging materials on seedling dry weight in Asossa during the main cropping season of 2019/2020

Percentage mean values of seedling dry weight					
PM	Storage month				
	0	6	12	18	24
G	0.31a	0.26ab	0.19fb-e	0.16d-f	0.16ef
MS	0.31a	0.25a-c	0.15f	0.16ef	0.15f
PC	0.31a	0.24a-e	0.19fb-e	0.16d-f	0.16ef
PE	0.31a	0.22b-f	0.21b-f	0.16d-f	0.16d-f
PP	0.31a	0.25a-d	0.19b-f	0.151f	0g
ZF	0.31a	0.22b-f	0.17c-f	0.15f	0g
CV	15.98				
HSD(0.05)	0.08				
F .value	<0.0001				

Means followed by the same letter within a column are not significantly different at 5% level of significance. HSD = Tukey's student zed range test; CV = Coefficient of variation; G = Super grain pro; MS = Metal silo; PP = Polypropylene; PE = Polypropylene bags with Polyethylene sheet lining; ZF = Zero fly; PC=PICS bag

3.3.3 Vigour Index

The interaction effect of packaging materials as well as that of duration of storage highly significantly ($P < 0.0001$) influenced seedling vigour index (Table 8). The highest (2738.85) and (24.86) vigour index I and II was recorded for seeds of Super grain bags after 12 months of stored respectively. On the other hand, the lowest (0) seedling VI and V-II value was obtained from seeds of Polypropylene bags and Zero fly packaging materials stored for 18 and 24 months respectively. Vigour Index was decreased as storage period increased for all air tight packaging materials where as significant reduction of vigour index-I observed for Polypropylene bags and Zero fly bags. The result of the experiment in line with Rao et al. (2006) who stated that packing materials, seed storage condition and duration of seed storage affects viability and vigor index.

Table 8 The interaction effect of storage period and packaging materials on V-I and V-II in Asossa during the main cropping season of 2019/2020

PM	Percentage mean values Storage month on VI and VII indexes									
	0		6		12		18		24	
	V-I	V-II	V-I	V-II	V-I	V-II	V-I	V-II	V-I	V-II
G	2216c	24.8a	2563.7a-c	14.16c-e	2738.85a	24.86a	2560.38a-c	17.85a-e	2369.94bc	15.55b-e
MS	2216c	24.8a	2536.6a-c	23.91a	2216c	14.75c-e	2531.4a-c	15.25c-e	2542.85a-c	12.67d-f
PC	2216c	24.8a	2568.88ab	22.9ab	2216c	18.09a-e	2483.91a-c	15.56b-e	2500.53a-c	14.63c-e
PE	2216c	24.8a	2278.1bc	20.86a-c	2216c	19.66a-d	2465.33a-c	15.12c-e	2252.19bc	15.11c-e
PP	2216c	24.8a	1332.99d	14.46c-e	1492.1d	11.81ef	19.91f	0g	0f	0g
ZF	2216c	24.8a	1351.14d	13.03d-f	932.84e	6.56fg	327.22f	2.19g	0f	0g
CV					6.58	17.2				
HSD (0.05)					349.7	7.50				
F. value					<0.0001	<0.0001				

Means followed by the same letter within a column are not significantly different at 5% level of significance. HSD = Tukey's student zed range test; CV = Coefficient of variation; G = Super grain pro; MS = Metal silo; PP = Polypropylene; PE = Polypropylene bags with Polyethylene sheet lining; ZF = Zero fly; PC=PICS bag; V-I= vigour index one; V-II=vigour index two

4. Conclusion

From the results, it may be concluded that packaging materials such as Super grain pro, Metal silo, PICS, and Polypropylene bags with Polyethylene sheet lining were found to be the best over that of Polypropylene and Zero fly bags which did not contain insect population and grain damage during entire storage period. Maximum moisture content, insect population and grain damage as well as minimum germination and seed vigour index of the seeds were recorded in Polypropylene and Zero fly bags. As the overall features of the study, it may be concluded that PICS bags followed by Metal silo, Super grain pro, and Polypropylene bags with Polyethylene sheet lining was observed to be best packaging material amongst all treatments having highest swelling capacity, germination and seed vigour index, no insect population, no grain damage and moderate moisture content of sorghum grain for twelve months of storage.

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